
Valid JSON, Wrong Answer: Per-Role Regression Detection and Linguistic Presupposition Labeling for Structured Output

Breck Baldwin
validjson.com
breck@validjson.com

Abstract

Generating reliable structured output from large language models, e.g., JSON of the form "apply_brake": "True", schema-conformant tool calls, or database queries, remains difficult in production. One possible fix pairs grammar-constrained decoding ('strict-json' mode to address syntax) with LoRA fine-tuning (to improve semantics), evaluated by aggregate loss. We observe *counter-current fields*: per-grammar-role components whose loss *rises* under fine-tuning even as aggregate loss falls.

Across Qwen 2.5 Instruct at three scales (0.5B, 7B, 32B) on Schema-Guided Dialogue (SGD) and the Contract Understanding Atticus Dataset (CUAD), we reproduce three signatures for **counter-current fields**:

- Aggregate loss falls 44–81% under fine-tuning, while boolean and enum-value roles increase loss on individual schemas (boolean on Flights, enum-value on CUAD).
- The effect is scale-dependent — on the boolean `refundable` field of a flight-booking schema, fine-tuning's gain shrinks from $-55%$ at 0.5B to $-3%$ at 7B and crosses into a $+12%$ regression at 32B.
- Counter-current tracks closely with what we call a *uniqueness presupposition*: training assumes each field's value is uniquely determined by the input, but in practice many examples lack the supporting evidence, and fine-tuning's gradient pulls the model toward the marginal distribution regardless of input.

We propose two mitigations rooted in this presupposition view:

- **Margin gating**, an inference-time technique that emits an `abstain` value when the model's top two predictions differ by less than a threshold θ . Improves precision for both baseline and fine tuned models with varied impact on recall.
- **Presupposition labeling**, a training-time technique that extends the schema with an `ambiguous` value and relabels training examples that lack supporting evidence. Reduces constrained-content loss by 21–58% across scales and eliminates the boolean regression at 7B and 32B.

We release code and data for reproduction.

1 Introduction

Getting consistent, high-quality JSON output from an LM has frustrated many a developer, from Reddit:

“I’ve been experimenting with using LLMs to generate structured outputs for downstream systems (JSON schemas, workflow configs, routing logic, etc.), and the biggest challenge isn’t getting a ‘good’ answer; it’s getting something consistently reliable enough for production.”¹

Grammar-constrained decoding Lundberg et al. [2024], Willard and Louf [2023], Zheng et al. [2024], Dong et al. [2024] solves the syntactic half (every generated token is schema-valid). Semantics is the hard half: a model can produce `{"refundable": "True"}` when the gold is `"False"` and remain schema-valid. The standard remedy is LoRA fine-tuning Hu et al. [2022] evaluated by aggregate loss; we show that aggregate loss mixes easily-correct decisions (structural tokens, whitespace) with substantively-uncertain decisions (enums, booleans), and that the latter can regress while the former carries the average. Practitioners who seek to improve JSON output beyond grammar-constrained decoding, perhaps with light fine-tuning to capture domain-specific field semantics, are the audience for our findings.

We fine-tune Qwen 2.5 Instruct at three scales (0.5B/7B/32B) on Schema-Guided Dialogue (SGD) Rastogi et al. [2020] and the Contract Understanding Atticus Dataset (CUAD) Hendrycks et al. [2021], and decompose per-token loss by JSON grammar role. We find:

- At 32B, fine-tuning degrades the boolean field `refundable` on a flight-booking schema by 12% while aggregate loss improves by 73%. The same field has regressed up to 130% on different seeds.
- The regression is scale-dependent: at 0.5B boolean performance improves 55%; at 7B the gain collapses to 3%; at 32B it regresses (+12%).
- On CUAD, fine-tuning makes enum-value prediction *worse* at every scale: loss rises by 18%, 38%, and 8% at 0.5B, 7B, and 32B, while aggregate loss falls 44–52%.
- A second SGD schema (restaurant booking) shows no regression — the phenomenon is schema- and data-dependent.

A bit of linguistic theory motivates the mitigations detailed below: the enums and booleans carry a *uniqueness presupposition* that can be exploited both at training time (presupposition labeling) and at inference time (margin gating). Code and data are released at <https://github.com/validjson/valid-json-wrong-answer>.

2 Contributions and Relation to Prior Work

We build on grammar-constrained decoding Lundberg et al. [2024], Willard and Louf [2023], Zheng et al. [2024], Dong et al. [2024], LoRA Hu et al. [2022], and per-class decomposition (per-class F1, confusion matrices). Our contributions:

- **Per-grammar-role decomposition for JSON** (§4): a formal treatment of an existing ad-hoc technique as post-hoc decomposition of teacher-forced loss by grammar role, applied systematically across three model scales and three schemas.
- **Counter-current fields** (§6.3): per-field loss *rises* under fine-tuning even as aggregate loss falls, and the regression is scale-dependent. We are aware of no prior published work documenting this for structured output.
- **Uniqueness presupposition** as the diagnostic frame (§7.2): a singular reference presupposes a unique referent; many training examples silently lack the evidence the presupposition assumes. First application of presupposition theory to structured-output labels, to our knowledge.
- **Margin gating** (§7.3): commit when the top-two probability margin exceeds θ , else emit abstain. A natural extension of selective prediction; we contribute the named recipe, threshold sweep, and demonstration that pretrained calibration alone is sufficient.
- **Presupposition labeling** (§7.2): the paper’s central contribution. A training-time relabel of evidentially-underdetermined examples to *ambiguous*, distinct from label smoothing (uniform softening) and *learn-to-abstain* (learned abstention): it targets specifically those

¹https://www.reddit.com/r/LLMDevs/comments/1szuqv7/how_are_people_making_llm_outputs_reliable_enough/

examples where input-evidence theory predicts the original label is artifactual. Eliminates the regression at 7B and 32B with no architectural change.

3 Background

Grammar-constrained decoding Lundberg et al. [2024], Willard and Louf [2023], Zheng et al. [2024], Dong et al. [2024] masks tokens that would violate the target grammar at decode time, guaranteeing schema-valid output. It prevents *syntactic* errors only – a model can still produce `{"refundable": "True"}` when the correct answer is `"False"`.

LoRA fine-tuning Hu et al. [2022] trains low-rank adapters on attention projections with cross-entropy on target sequences and is typically evaluated by aggregate loss. The implicit assumption that aggregate improvement entails uniform per-role improvement is what we show to be violated.

JSON grammar roles. A JSON document carries tokens of distinct roles: *structural* (`{ } [] : ,` whitespace, quotes), *key*, *enum* (categorical from a fixed set), *boolean* (`True/False`), and *free text*. Roles differ in both difficulty and token budget: structural and whitespace are near-deterministic and dominate token counts, while boolean and enum values carry genuine semantic uncertainty in fewer tokens. Aggregate loss therefore mixes signals of very different reliability.

4 Method: Per-Grammar-Role Decomposition

Given a JSON string and its schema, we assign each *character* a grammar role with a recursive-descent parser that tracks key vs. value position and field type. We then tokenize with the model’s standard BPE tokenizer and assign each token the role of its first character; tokens spanning multiple roles (e.g. `": "`) are a known limitation of post-hoc analysis. The dominant content roles (`KEY`, `ENUM`, `FREE_TEXT`) rarely share tokens with others, and boolean values had a 1-to-1 token-terminal mapping across all three Qwen scales, so the regression we report is not an artifact of surface tokenization.

For each example we compute teacher-forced per-token cross-entropy on the target JSON (prompt tokens masked), then aggregate by role: $\mathcal{L}_r = |T_r|^{-1} \sum_{t \in T_r} \ell(t)$, where T_r is the set of tokens assigned to role r . The method works with any fine-tuned model, schema, and tokenizer; the analysis adds negligible overhead (a single forward pass with token-level loss recording).

5 Experimental Setup

5.1 Data

We use three schemas across two corpora.

Restaurants_1 (Schema-Guided Dialogue Rastogi et al. [2020], 11 keys): 3 enum fields (cuisine, price_range, party_size), 2 boolean fields (serves_alcohol, has_live_music), 6 free-text fields. An intuitive domain with moderate schema complexity.

Flights_1 (Schema-Guided Dialogue Rastogi et al. [2020], 16 keys): 4 enum fields (passengers, seating_class, number_stops, airlines), 1 boolean field (refundable), 11 free-text fields. A complex domain with a high-cardinality enum (8 airlines).

CUAD (Contract Understanding Atticus Dataset Hendrycks et al. [2021], 11 keys): a document-level extraction task built from 510 commercial contracts with human-annotated clause-level labels. Eight boolean clause-presence indicators with Yes-rates spanning 4–78%, plus three normalized enum fields (governing_law, 12 values; renewal_term, 6; expiration_type, 3). The enum fields include a `not_specified` value – the natural analog of the ambiguous label introduced for presupposition labeling (Section 7.2). Inputs are contract excerpts (~2k tokens), considerably longer than the dialogue schemas (~0.5k tokens).

Splits: 250 train / 50 test for the SGD schemas; 144 train / 49 test for CUAD (stratified by total True-count on booleans). Each SGD example pairs a dialogue context with a service-result JSON object; each CUAD example pairs a contract excerpt with the 11-field JSON.

Schema	Scale	Base	FT	Change
Rest.	0.5B	0.969	0.402	−59%
	7B	1.090	0.382	−65%
	32B	0.856	0.368	−57%
Flights	0.5B	0.733	0.139	−81%
	7B	0.645	0.148	−77%
	32B	0.554	0.150	−73%
CUAD	0.5B	0.239	0.133	−44%
	7B	0.308	0.146	−52%
	32B	0.267	0.138	−48%

Table 1: Aggregate mean loss (all grammar roles). Fine-tuning improves every condition across all three schemas. Standard evaluation sees no problems.

5.2 Models and Training

We use Qwen 2.5 Instruct at three scales: 0.5B, 7B, and 32B parameters. Fine-tuning uses standard LoRA via PEFT Mangrulkar et al. [2023]: rank 16, alpha 32, targeting `q_proj` and `v_proj`, trained for 10 epochs with learning rate 10^{-4} . No custom adapter architectures or training modifications.

Grammar-constrained decoding uses `llguidance` Lundberg et al. [2024] at inference time. All models produce 100% valid JSON on held-out data.

Run-to-run variation. LoRA on these dataset sizes (144–250 examples) is sensitive to RNG state. Across four training runs of Flights at 32B we observed boolean FT loss values of 0.510, 0.556, 0.722, 0.824 — a 60% spread — against a stable base of 0.457. The *sign* of the effect survives every run; magnitudes do not. We pin the seed (`−seed 42`) so reviewers reproduce table values exactly; aggregate loss rests on a token-weighted average of these noisy per-role estimates, which is part of why it looks stable. Per-role *patterns* generalize; magnitudes do not.

6 Problem Analysis

6.1 Aggregate Metrics Tell a Positive Story

Table 1 shows aggregate loss improvement across all conditions. Fine-tuning produces improvements at every scale on every schema: 44–81% reduction in mean loss, with the smaller CUAD deltas reflecting a stronger pretrained baseline on document-level inputs (CUAD’s base loss is already 0.24–0.31, well below the dialogue schemas). All fine-tuned models produce valid JSON. Standard evaluation says: fine-tuning works.

6.2 Per-Grammar-Role Decomposition Reveals a Hidden Regression

Table 2 decomposes loss by grammar role for the Flights schema. At 32B, boolean prediction loss *increases* from 0.457 to 0.510—a 12% degradation—while aggregate loss decreases 73%. The 12% is mild in absolute terms, but the trend across scales (Section 6.3) shows the boolean role losing all of its fine-tuning gain by 7B and crossing into outright regression at 32B.

The Flights schema has one boolean field: `refundable` (True/False). At 32B, the pretrained model predicts this field reasonably well (0.457 loss). Fine-tuning disrupts this: the model most likely overfits to the majority boolean value in the training data, producing worse predictions than the untrained baseline.

6.3 The Regression can be Scale-Dependent

Table 3 shows boolean prediction change across model scales on the Flights schema:

At 0.5B, the base model is poor at boolean prediction (0.799 loss) and fine-tuning helps substantially (−55%). At 7B, the base model is already much better (0.432) and fine-tuning’s marginal gain has

Role	0.5B		7B		32B	
	Base	FT	Base	FT	Base	FT
STRUCT	4.84	0.00	6.08	0.00	5.33	0.00
QUOTE	0.12	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.10	0.00
KEY	1.17	0.00	0.77	0.00	0.47	0.00
ENUM	0.48	0.19	0.55	0.38	0.33	0.23
BOOL	0.80	0.36	0.43	0.42	0.46	0.51
FREE	1.31	0.52	1.26	0.53	1.33	0.56
WS	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.02	0.00
TOTAL	0.73	0.14	0.64	0.15	0.55	0.15

Table 2: Flights: per-grammar-role loss at three scales. At 32B, boolean loss **rises 12%** while aggregate loss decreases 73%; the per-role view also reveals the 7B boolean stagnation ($-3%$, vs $-55%$ at 0.5B). Both signals are invisible without decomposition.

Scale	Base	FT	Change
0.5B	0.799	0.361	$-55%$
7B	0.432	0.419	$-3%$
32B	0.457	0.510	+12%

Table 3: Boolean (refundable) loss on Flights across scales. At 0.5B, fine-tuning helps substantially. At 7B, the gain has essentially vanished. At 32B, fine-tuning crosses into outright regression. Larger models have more to lose.

collapsed to noise ($-3%$). At 32B, fine-tuning crosses into a true regression: the model emerges worse at boolean prediction than the untrained baseline.

In more detail, training data contains 76% False, 24% True for the refundable field. A naive majority-class predictor on this distribution has expected loss 0.55; the 32B base model is below this floor (0.46), implying it does carry some signal beyond the prior. After fine-tuning, the 32B boolean loss rises to 0.51 — close to the calibrated-prior floor. Fine-tuning has not driven the model to a degenerate constant predictor, but it has eroded the input-conditional signal the base model had: the per-example variance that distinguished True-evidence-present from True-evidence-absent inputs has been smoothed toward the prior.

The pattern is intuitive: larger pretrained models have stronger existing competencies. Fine-tuning on a small dataset (250 examples) can override these competencies with memorized patterns. The better the base model already is, the more fine-tuning has to disrupt.

6.4 Enumeration Values Regress Across Scale on CUAD

The boolean regression on Flights is matched by an enum-value regression on CUAD. Where Flights enum loss improves at every scale ($-60%$, $-31%$, $-30%$ from 0.5B to 32B), CUAD’s enum-value loss *worsens* at every scale:

Scale	Base	FT	Change
0.5B	0.976	1.154	+18%
7B	0.862	1.189	+38%
32B	0.966	1.046	+8%

Table 4: Enum-value loss on CUAD across scales (averaged over the three enum fields: `governing_law`, `renewal_term`, `expiration_type`). Fine-tuning regresses at every scale, with the largest degradation at 7B.

The mechanism is the same as for Flights’ boolean: CUAD’s enums are dominated by `not_specified` for many fields (the *uniqueness presupposition* fails when the contract excerpt does not mention a governing law), and fine-tuning amplifies the majority-class bias. Two regressions

Role	0.5B		7B		32B	
	Base	FT	Base	FT	Base	FT
STRUCT	4.94	0.00	6.25	0.00	5.52	0.00
QUOTE	0.22	0.04	0.33	0.03	0.17	0.03
KEY	1.21	0.00	1.32	0.00	0.67	0.00
ENUM	1.73	0.36	1.70	0.64	1.59	0.37
BOOL	0.81	0.57	1.24	0.56	0.74	0.50
FREE	1.76	1.22	1.86	1.13	1.71	1.12
WS	0.02	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.03	0.00
TOTAL	0.97	0.40	1.09	0.38	0.86	0.37

Table 5: Restaurants: per-grammar-role loss at three scales. No role regresses. The Flights boolean and CUAD enum regressions are schema- and data-dependent.

in two grammar roles on two different schemas: per-role decomposition is needed to see either, and the aggregate-loss view in Table 1 hides both (−44% to −81% improvements all the way down).

6.5 Per-Field Behavior Varies by Schema and by Field Alignment

The Flights regression is not universal. Table 5 shows the Restaurants schema, where *no role regresses* at any scale.

Whether a field regresses depends on the schema, the training distribution, and the base model’s prior alignment with the majority gold class. CUAD’s eight booleans span 4–78% True gold rates and partition by alignment with the base default (False):

Field	0.5B	7B	32B
has_most_favored_nation	94% (0.37)	96% (0.90)	94% (0.93)
has_liquidated_damages	86% (0.51)	92% (0.73)	90% (0.83)
has_exclusivity	67% (0.24)	86% (0.76)	92% (0.79)
has_anti_assignment	27% (0.19)	22% (0.99)	35% (0.93)
governing_law (12-way)	16% (0.20)	24% (0.57)	27% (0.69)
renewal_term (6-way)	2% (0.45)	53% (0.64)	55% (0.70)
expiration_type (3-way)	49% (0.26)	67% (0.68)	63% (0.76)

Table 6: CUAD baseline accuracy (mean top prob – 2nd prob) across scales for selected fields. Regressions in red. Fields whose majority gold class aligns with the base model’s default (top three rows) are stable across scale; fields whose majority gold class is the opposite (*has_anti_assignment*, 78% True) show non-monotonic regression, e.g., drop to 22% at high confidence 99% at 7B. *renewal_term* shows scale-dependent acquisition of the *not_specified* sentinel between 0.5B and 7B.

Aligned-majority fields (top of Table 6) are stable across scale; misaligned-majority fields reproduce Flights’ failure mode in a different costume — confidently more wrong at intermediate scale, partially recovering at 32B. Aggregate CUAD accuracy rises monotonically with scale, hiding both shapes; per-field decomposition is necessary because one cannot predict *which* field will regress without measuring.

6.6 Why Aggregate Metrics Hide the Regression

The aggregate is a token-weighted average and trivial roles contribute far more tokens than substantive ones. Concretely, in the Flights 32B case the 1,950 whitespace and 100 structural tokens both go from non-zero to 0.00 loss while the 50 boolean tokens regress from 0.46 to 0.51; the high-token-count “wins” swamp the low-token-count “loss” in any token-weighted summary. Per-role decomposition recovers the signal by reporting each role on its own.

7 Discussion

7.1 Why the Boolean Regresses: Lexical Analysis

We categorize each Flights training example by whether the conversation contains lexical evidence for refundability (cue search on “refund”):

Context	True	False
Refundability discussed (57 examples)	47%	53%
Not discussed (193 examples)	17%	83%

Table 7: refundable value distribution conditioned on lexical support. When discussed, roughly balanced. When not discussed, the field is an API-side property with no conversational cue.

In 77% of training examples (193/250) refundability is never mentioned — the field is an API result with no input cue. 54% of all True cases (32/59) have *no lexical support*; the correct prediction for these cases is honest uncertainty (loss $-\log(0.5) = 0.69$). The fine-tuned 32B boolean loss of 0.51 sits near the calibrated-prior floor (0.55 for the 76/24 base rate): fine-tuning has pulled the model toward predicting the marginal regardless of input. Gradient signal from 193 undiscussable examples washes out the 57 examples with genuine evidence, leaving the model close to a constant predictor and slightly worse than the input-conditioned base.

Speculatively, the cool reception of fine-tuning in some JSON-generation playbooks may itself be the residue of regressions like these — a failure felt in production tests but invisible to the aggregate loss usually reported.

7.2 Presupposition Labeling: A Mitigation

The lexical analysis suggests a mitigation: if the input does not provide evidence for a field’s value, the training label should reflect this rather than forcing a commitment. We draw on the *uniqueness presupposition* from pronoun resolution Baldwin [1997]: a singular pronoun presupposes exactly one valid referent; when multiple referents are equally valid, the system should abstain rather than guess as a useful quality of inference.

Applied to structured output: for each constrained field, we ask whether the input provides sufficient evidence to determine the value. If not, we relabel the training target as ambiguous — a third option alongside the original values. For the refundable field, the 57 examples where refundability is discussed retain their True/False labels; the 193 examples where it is not discussed are relabeled to ambiguous. The schema is updated accordingly: refundable: ["True", "False", "ambiguous"].

We call this **presupposition labeling**: expanding the label set based on whether the input satisfies the evidential presupposition for a field’s value.

Scale	2-way Std LoRA	Random-ambig (3-way, random)	PCL (3-way, cue-driven)	Change PCL vs 2-way
0.5B	0.217	0.338	0.171	−21%
7B	0.382	0.287	0.162	−58%
32B	0.266	0.276	0.146	−45%

Table 8: Constrained-content loss (BOOLEAN+ENUM combined, token-weighted) on Flights under three training regimes. The combined bucket is necessary because both 3-way conditions relabel refundable as a 3-value enum, moving its tokens from the BOOLEAN to the ENUM_VALUE role; the same 360 constrained-content tokens are scored under all three schemas. **Random-ambig** is a control that relabels 193/250 = 77.2% of training examples to ambiguous uniformly at random — the same overall rate as cue-driven PCL .

Table 8 reports a 21–58% reduction in constrained-content loss across scales, including 45% at 32B where std-LoRA had pushed the boolean role into regression. Only the training labels change; no architectural modifications. The mechanism is schema-mediated rather than human-mediated: the

schema defines what values are *structurally* valid; a presupposition check determines whether the input *evidentially licenses* a commitment. In our experiments the check is a lexical cue (“refund” for `refundable`); more sophisticated checks could derive automatically from input–field mutual information.

A natural concern is whether PCL’s improvement reflects the cue-driven relabeling specifically, or whether any introduction of an abstain class at the same rate would suffice. The **random-ambig** column of Table 8 answers this: relabeling the same 77.2% of training examples to ambiguous uniformly at random — discarding the cue — is *worse* than 2-way std LoRA at 0.5B (0.338 vs. 0.217) and at 32B (0.276 vs. 0.266), and only modestly helpful at 7B (0.287 vs. 0.382) where std-LoRA was already heavily regressed. PCL beats random-ambig by 41–49% at every scale. Adding an abstain class without a principled cue can actively confuse the model; the gain is contingent on relabeling the right examples, not merely on relabeling at the right rate.

CUAD: field-specific variance. On CUAD’s 11 fields, PCL-FT’s benefit concentrates on fields whose pretrained prior conflicts with the task (`has_anti_assignment` 35→61%, `governing_law` 25→39% at 32B); fields whose prior was already correct see neutral effect; and three fields *regress* (e.g. `expiration_type` 57→39% at 32B). The regressing fields share a property: their diagnostic clauses sit deeper in the contract than the 8000-character training-time truncation we use. Re-evaluating the same 32B PCL-FT checkpoint on full-context test contracts lifts aggregate accuracy 71→85% and recovers the regressions (`expiration_type` 39→53%). PCL-FT is not a uniform win; per-field evaluation remains necessary, and training-time truncation choices determine which fields it can rescue.

7.3 Margin-Based Evidential Gating at Inference Time

Presupposition labeling fixes the regression at training time. A complementary question: is the evidential signal already in the pretrained distribution, exploitable without fine-tuning? At each constrained-field position we measure the margin $m = p_1 - p_2$ over the field’s allowed values, commit when $m \geq \theta$, and abstain otherwise.

Group	Gold = True/False top prob – 2nd	Gold = ambiguous top prob – 2nd	baseline acc
Discussed (Flights, $n = 17$)	0.36	—	35%
Undiscussed (Flights, $n = 33$)	—	0.22	0% (forced commit)

Table 9: Base Qwen 2.5 0.5B, Flights `refundable`. The top-vs-2nd probability gap nearly doubles when the input contains lexical evidence and stays flat when the field is underspecified — the signal for evidential gating is present in the base model.

On Flights, the margin discriminates discussed from undiscussed examples cleanly (Table 9). At pos-hoc $\theta = 0.35$ the base model abstains on 100% of undiscussed golds while retaining 71% committed accuracy on the discussed subset (up from 43% under forced commitment). On CUAD’s `expiration_type` the same operating point reaches 76% abstention on `not_specified` golds and 82% committed accuracy on the rest.

Not every field cooperates: on CUAD’s `renewal_term` the base model’s 0.5B distribution places near-zero probability on the `not_specified` token (0% abstention, 2% accuracy); the model learns the sentinel between 0.5B and 7B (53%/55% accuracy at 7B/32B) but never closes the gap to the 66% gold rate. Schema-level sentinels are scale-sensitive; PCL at training time is the remaining lever.

7.4 Head-to-Head: Training-Time and Inference-Time Interventions

Overall results are what no developer wants to hear—it’s complicated. PCL-FT helps in every row (+19/+19 on Flights, +38/+30 on Restaurants, +6/+10 on CUAD where truncation cuts off cue evidence). Gating adds 0–7 pp on top of PCL-FT for 1–21 pp of coverage; the two are non-redundant. The largest gating-only lifts are 0.5B and 32B Flights (58→74% @68%, 72→84% @82%) — small models where fine-tuning is impractical, large models where calibration is preserved. Field-isolated: PCL-FT lifts Flights `refundable` from 12/26/26%→98/98/96% argmax at 0.5B/7B/32B (gating adds nothing); on CUAD enums combined, 22→43% at 0.5B and 48→56% at 32B (neutral at

Dataset	Scale	Baseline		PCL-FT	
		argmax	+ gate ($\theta=0.30$)	argmax	+ gate ($\theta=0.30$)
Flights	0.5B	58%	74% @68%	88%	93% @91%
Flights	7B	71%	72% @96%	90%	93% @93%
Flights	32B	72%	84% @82%	91%	92% @93%
Restaurants	0.5B	31%	39% @58%	80%	87% @91%
Restaurants	7B	45%	48% @93%	83%	86% @96%
Restaurants	32B	52%	52% @92%	82%	82% @99%
CUAD	0.5B	56%	63% @57%	66%	73% @79%
CUAD	7B	65%	68% @90%	71%	78% @83%
CUAD	32B	66%	68% @91%	76%	80% @90%

Table 10: Aggregate accuracy across all constrained fields, per dataset \times scale. Argmax columns are argmax accuracy; gated columns are “committed accuracy @ coverage”.

7B). The recall price is real: under abstain-as-failure scoring, effective accuracy is bounded by committed \times coverage, and PCL-FT argmax matches or beats PCL-FT + gate in every row. Use gating when abstention has a downstream path; use PCL-FT argmax when commit-or-fail is required.

7.5 Open Directions and Deployment Implications

Presupposition labeling addresses regressions caused by underspecified inputs; other sources — gradient domination by trivial tokens, enum overfitting — may need different interventions (per-role learning rate schedules, per-role early stopping, training-time structural awareness). Any structured-output task that mixes trivially-correct with substantively-uncertain decisions inherits the counter-current vulnerability; per-grammar-role thresholds (e.g., deploy when STRUCTURAL < 0.01 , flag when ENUM > 0.3 , require human review when BOOLEAN > 0.5) are more informative than aggregate thresholds and cost one additional forward pass per evaluation example.

8 Conclusion

Aggregate loss hides counter-current fields whose loss *rises* under fine-tuning. The regressions are scale-dependent and traceable to what can be analyzed as a uniqueness-presupposition violation in training labels but that is far from proven. *Presupposition labeling* fixes it at training time; *margin gating* catches residual under-confident commitments at inference; neither requires architectural change so some progress can be made with existing tooling and infrastructure but we could use more progress in the direction of reliable structured generation as LLM assume greater significance in our infrastructure.

Acknowledgments

References

- Breck Baldwin. CogNIAC: High precision coreference with limited knowledge and linguistic resources. In *Operational Factors in Practical, Robust Anaphora Resolution for Unrestricted Texts, ACL Workshop*, 1997.
- Yixin Dong et al. XGrammar: Flexible and efficient structured generation engine for large language models, 2024.
- Dan Hendrycks, Collin Burns, Anya Chen, and Spencer Ball. CUAD: An expert-annotated NLP dataset for legal contract review. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2103.06268*, 2021.
- Edward J Hu, Yelong Shen, Phillip Wallis, Zeyuan Allen-Zhu, Yuanzhi Li, Shean Wang, Lu Wang, and Weizhu Chen. LoRA: Low-rank adaptation of large language models. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2022.

- Scott Lundberg et al. Guidance: A language for controlling large language models, 2024. Microsoft Research. <https://github.com/guidance-ai/guidance>.
- Sourab Mangrulkar, Sylvain Gugger, Lysandre Debrau, Julien Launay, and Sayak Paul. PEFT: State-of-the-art parameter-efficient fine-tuning, 2023. HuggingFace. <https://github.com/huggingface/peft>.
- Abhinav Rastogi, Xiaoxue Zang, Srinivas Sber, Raghav Guber, and Nikola Mrkšić. Towards scalable multi-domain conversational agents: The schema-guided dialogue dataset. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2020.
- Brandon T Willard and Rémi Louf. Efficient guided generation for large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.09702*, 2023.
- Lianmin Zheng, Liangsheng Yin, Zhiqiang Xie, et al. SGLang: Efficient execution of structured language model programs, 2024.